

TYPES OF TONGUE TWISTERS ACCORDING TO TEXT COMPOSITION AND NATURE

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Abstract: This article discusses the terms representing the genre of tongue twisters, which is one of the ancient genres of the Uzbek, Karakalpak, and Turkic peoples, as well as the types of folk tongue twisters according to their text composition and nature, and their specific features.

Keywords: tongue twister, genre, folklore, term

Entrance

Among the Uzbek people, tongue-twisters are called "tutal," "chalg'itma," "chalg'ituv," "chalish," "adashish"[1: 169], among other Turkic peoples: among the Karakalpaks and Kazakhs - "jañiltpash," among the Kyrgyz - "жаңылмач," "жаңылтмач," "бат айтма," "тил сындырмак," among the Turkmens - "ýañyltmaç," "ýeñyltmeç," among the Tatars - "тизэйткеч," "тил чаплантиргич," "телкөрмәвеч," "тел бэйләндергеч," "тел көрмәкләндергеч," among the Crimean Tatars - "тезайтым " or "тезайтув," among the Azerbaijanis - "yaniltmac," "çaşdırma (ca)," "dildolaşdırma (ca)," among the Ottoman Turks - "yaniltmaç (a)," "şaşırmac (a)," "şaşırtmaç," among the Gagauz people "yaniltmaç," "şaşırtma," "dil dolaştırma (k)," "dil kösteklemä (k)," "dil kırmak," among the Kumyks "янгылтмач," among the Karachay-Balkar people "джангытхыч," "тилбургъуч," among the Bashkirs "телкөрмәүес," "тизэйткес," among the Nogais "янъылтпаш," among the Yakuts "чабыргах," among the Altai people "modor sös," among the Russian people "скороговорка," among the Tajiks "тезгўяк."

Literature analysis and methods

If you pay attention, you can see that in almost all Turkic-speaking peoples, the terms expressing the genre of tongue twisters are close in meaning and function. Such closeness indicates that the foundation of these Turkic peoples goes back to a common ancestral language. In the process of intensive pronunciation of a text consisting of a series of words that are difficult to pronounce quickly, consisting of a complex sound system, such phenomena as confusion, distraction, error, and stuttering are observed in speech. The above-

mentioned terms indicate that this genre is based on such aspects (speaking quickly, making mistakes, breaking the tongue).

The complex structure, the reliance on distraction in performance, is an important feature of the fast-paced genre. It's hard to imagine it without them. In this regard, i.e., depending on the occurrence of the phenomenon of distraction, we conditionally classified tongue twisters as follows:

Results And Discussion

In tongue twisters based on distraction, the text has a complex structure, in which adjacent sounds, harmonious, harmonious words, and various adjectives participate. Such pronouncements are based solely on pronunciation distortion. For example:

Bu bog'cha boshqa bog'cha[2].

Karakalpak tongue twister:

Jaqsı qayshı,

Qaysı qayshı[3: 18].

Although the given examples consist of four words, they are not easy to pronounce quickly. In the Uzbek example, the words "bo'g'cha" and "boshqa" are not placed side by side for nothing. If the place of "sh" and "q" in the word "boshqa" is changed, the word "boqsha," consonant with the word "bo'g'cha," is formed. Thus, in performance, these words harmonize with each other. Secondly, the sounds "sh" and "ch" in the text mix during performance. A similar situation is observed in the Karakalpak example. The words "qaysı" and "qayshı" in the text differ by one phoneme. In the performance process, this difference is eliminated as a result of the agreement of two words, and one of them is pronounced.

Osmonda ikkita dumi kalta kal kalxat, birining ko'k dumi kalta kal kalxat, birining qora dumi kalta kal kalxat. Ko'k dumi kalta kal kalxat qora dumi kalta kal kalxatga xalaqit beradimi, qora dumi kalta kal kalxat ko'k dumi kalta kal kalxatga xalaqit beradimi[4: 61].

This sample has a complex structure with a large number of distracting elements. This includes various elements that distract the performer, such as the number, color, and parts of the vultures, as well as words like "kalta," "kal," and "kalxat." Therefore, it's natural for the performer to make mistakes at certain points during the performance process.

Tongue twisters, in which the meaning of the word changes, were in the repertoire of adults in ancient times. We discussed this issue in the adults' speeches. When such examples are performed, words that are absent in the text

are accidentally spoken, or rather, their meaning changes during the performance process. As we noted above, special words are selected for the text of such tongue twisters. For example, when the phrase "Namanganlik To'lagan to'la lagan handalak yegan[5: 406] is said rapidly, the pause between the words "to'la" and "lagan" disappears, and when two words are added, one of them is dropped because the last syllable of the first word and the first syllable of the second word are the same. As a result, it sounds like "Namanganlik To'lagan to'lagan handalak yegan."

Oq toy oqmi?

Qora toy oqmi?[6]

This tongue-twister also exists among the Karakalpak, Kyrgyz, and Kazakh peoples, which is also based on a change in meaning during performance.

Tongue twisters based on wordplay (tajnisli) are constructed using the art of tajnis. In these tongue twisters, words that are identical in form but have different meanings are used:

Olma shoxida Olmaxon,

Olmaxonni olma, Olmaxon![7: 201]

Although the words "olma" and "Olmaxon" in this tongue twister have the same form, they serve to express two different meanings. The word "olma" in the first line means a fruit, in the second - a command, and the word "Olmaxon" in the first line means an animal, in the second - a person.

Apam kóylegime,

Jaña jag'a saldı.

Jaña jag'anı,

Jaña saldı[3: 29].

More:

Miywagúldiń bag'ındag'ı miyweler,

Jılında úsh máhál miyweler[8: 445].

In the Karakalpak example, the word "jaña" means new in one place and just now in another, while in the second example, the word "miyweler" means fruits - fruit trees in the first line, and fruits - fruits in the second line.

Result

As can be seen from the above thoughts, yanglishmoq is a very ancient Turkic word, and the term expressing the genre of tongue twisters in Turkic peoples originated from this word. Also, although this genre is currently known in Uzbek folklore as tongue twister, its essence lies in confusion, misleading, and

misleading. The reason is that the purpose of performing a quick recitation was also to confuse and mislead the performer in ancient times.

In conclusion, a complex structure, based on distraction in performance, is an important feature of the genre of fast singing, without which it is difficult to imagine it. From this point of view, that is, depending on the occurrence of the phenomenon of confusion, we determined that there are types of tongue twisters based on confusion, where the meaning of the word changes, and tajnis (based on wordplay) depending on the composition and nature of the text.

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